

**THE INFLUENCE OF INTERCULTURAL INTERACTION ON THE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.**

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Abstract: Pedagogical possibilities of the impact of intercultural relations on the educational and production process are determined by cultural and educational factors that allow social development to do this. Culture and higher education are obvious goals. Each country's own culture is more valuable than other cultures for its people and educational system. The person tends to multiculturalism and prefers to value different registers. Many cultural ambivalences and affiliations can be identified in all of us. Spiritual evolution is the result of plurality, and mixture is the result of singular views. A school should be based on the internal plurality of culture, like the management of a social institution, to satisfy the aspirations of different individuals. The first step towards understanding and accepting others is knowledge and respect for cultural diversity.

Keyword: education, culture, interculturalism, multiculturalism,

cultural pluralism.

This article emphasizes the importance of education and culture in our development as human beings, and the development in the digital age is the result of increasing the effectiveness of education through practical application of education. Educational problems under the dome of globalization and migration. is

becoming different. In this new world, it will be very important to accept the different experiences of others. This article is an attempt to clarify some of the reasons for the difficulties encountered in education, suggests the identification of barriers to intercultural education, and offers recommendations for teachers to promote interculturality in this field in general. From the point of view of social dynamics, the mandate of education plays very seriously in our country and in the world in general, these are: to adequately respond to differences, to the right to equality, to provide effective solutions that promote diversity in schools. The work Education, culture and intercultural relations focuses on interethnic relations, communication between different cultures, and the role of education in the context of diversity. Modern society emphasizes the role and purpose of school in a pluralistic world based on diversity. In such a world, who should change: the school or the students? This article emphasizes the idea that we should respect the differences between students, that education should be open to all, regardless of their cultural, ethnic, religious, social development. Also emphasized is the valence of embracing diversity in intercultural education or multicultural interaction.

Understanding the state of culture in modern societies, better communication with representatives of other cultures, adaptive attitude to cultural diversity, open mind for social interaction.

The article contains references to the role of education, its role in culture and social interaction, and creative individuals focused on

common humanity. It promotes equality, the value of diversity, social, justice and the equal distribution of power among different ethnic groups.

Multiculturalism in education is rich and complex, revealing differences that arise from the focus of the learning environment or teaching methods. Of course, intercultural education should be based on democratic values that promote cultural pluralism in a diverse society and a changing world. Multiculturalism is used to describe static situations, while interculturalism refers to interaction rather than interaction.

The goal of intercultural education diversity is education for all.

The development of intercultural education in Europe is industrialized

It is the result of pressures on institutions by the waves of immigrants that started in the countries after the Second World War. In the 1960s and 1970s, it developed rapidly due to the presence of migrants in Western European countries. Today, diversity issues are embedded in education policy and practice.

Social, economic, political, management is a necessary communication in any matter, be it managers, experts, politicians, members of international organizations or ordinary people.

When contact occurs between individuals, groups, or human ethnic communities, with different histories and cultural roots, we are dealing with intercultural communication. All relations between cultures are economic, social, political, organizational, including cultural relations established on the basis of agreements, bilateral or multilateral agreements between institutions, offices, enterprises, organizations and human communities in different countries.

In Europe and beyond, in America and Canada, anywhere in the world. Emphasizing the professional mobility of labor, increasing the percentage of people who have the opportunity to travel around the world are other examples of contacts between cultures, the culture of mutual knowledge and the civilization of other peoples, etc. Direct

contact with other ways of life is useful because it changes and deepens knowledge in different areas of life, traveling means relaxation, but most importantly, it exposes people to other people's lives, cultures and lifestyles. real (or electronic) that informs and convinces the style organizes libraries.

Our century is essentially an era of intercultural contact based on the large-scale process of European integration and globalization. In the field of communication between cultures, the relations between peoples and countries, which are part of their entire cultural wealth, are spiritual and human in these new trends.

Thus, we reach the connection between individuals as the "raw material" of nations and peoples, and all of them are carriers of cultural models with their own trajectories of social life. (Cobianu-Bacanu, 2006)

The final conclusions of the article are that people, human groups, peoples and nations benefit from the contact between cultures, and therefore they are rightfully considered, from the heights of their material and cultural achievements by building a national and international environment. They use Peace, understanding and cooperation are needed to solve collective problems or the global community. On a global scale, this communication is a form of transition from conflicts to a dialogue of civilizations and cultures, and their educational and intercultural relations are effective benefits for all parties, because it is important because it shows the possibility of creating a strong true human solidarity.

The main concepts are education, culture, interculturalism, cultural pluralism, intercultural communication, intercultural education, making them indispensable definition and clarification. According to the dictionary of education, sociology, social movement is a set of cultural transmission, generation, organization and management of individual or collective education. It can be formal or informal (Zamfir & Vlasceanu, 1993).

From a sociological perspective, education can be seen as both a system and a process. The educational system reflects the relationship between the world social system and the educational system.

A systematic approach to education allows for a high level of illumination of the specific functions and structures of the institution.

The educational system is an open system (in relation to the global social system), has a teleological character (to a certain finality, medium and long term), self-regulating and entropy, chaos, including for optimization. has opportunities.

The analysis of the educational system from the point of view of the sociology of education <<allows to determine the development of the individual in the teaching of the educational institution in terms of theories aimed at explaining

the process of socialization, which is a process of various subjective and objective social integration with tools.

There are several approaches to value education: axiological, economic, sociological, political, etc. There is a difference between economic behavior and the evaluation of its components and activities that require people to produce for a long time.

Social norms, rules, human capital, social capital, professional the continuous diffusion of concepts such as competence cannot act outside of values. The role of education and training is very important in a civilized society. First of all, education contributes to the formation and development of a person. But the level of economic development of the country depends on their education. Citizens, therefore requires a clear vision of the role of education in society.

Social paradigm- knowledge higher education institutions than ever before also emphasizes that they are more important because they are a means of developing the global economy.

In the globalized world, where continuous changes are taking place in general and higher education in particular, these factors are strongly

influenced by certain socio-demographic characteristics such as the population, the number of demographic phenomena (recruitment), the development of information, technology, financial capital, etc. is showing.

Culture is meaningful, socially inherited, and diverse a set of behaviors and symbols transmitted through practices; a system of representation, a system through which people communicate and develop their knowledge and attitudes towards life. Cultural pluralism emerged as a result of the study of societies divided by ethnic, racial, religious and ideological norms and

It is the coexistence of several types of political culture in the society includes (Zamfir and Vlăsceanu, 1993). Interculturalism refers to supporting intercultural communication and challenging self-separating tendencies in cultures

(Multiculturalism's Double Bind: Creating Inclusivity, Cosmopolitanism and Difference, 2009).

Intercultural communication is a form of communication designed to exchange information between different cultures and social groups. The term is used to describe a wide range of communicative processes and problems that naturally occur in an organization composed of people from different religious, social, ethnic, and educational backgrounds. Intercultural education is the result of symbiosis between education and culture. The first type of cross-cultural research in education is concerned with the transfer of culture and the impact and role of minority status in school contexts. The cultural context of the classroom is an important topic in anthropology education in two ways: microethnographic and macroethnographic. Micro-ethnographic studies focus on issues such as student/student, teacher/student teaching, and teacher role relationships.

Macro-ethnographic studies based on representative school-community relations in Warren's monograph on education in Germany (Rebhausen) and Singleton's monograph on the Japanese school in the first half of the 20th century were opened only to cross-cultural

ethnographic research due to economic and political constraints. Nowadays, increased opportunities have facilitated the advancement of science and technology in the field of communication. Researchers can work with colleagues on intercultural education.

Culture determines the behavior of a person, adaptation to historical, socio-economic and environmental problems. These are the emergence of two phenomena: cultural transmission; and acculturation (the phenomenon of transfer of behavioral values from one group to another as a result of contact between two groups).

The degree of acculturation is compulsory school years, work and daily interactions, activities with another cultural group determined by age, socio-economic situation. Enculturation involves the transmission of that group's culture

to generations for optimal integration, while socialization refers to the changes that occur in the environment and encounters with each other. This includes all voluntary testing and awareness. A culture is different from and valuable to other cultures. Individuals are multicultural and nurture mixed values. Knowledge is the first step towards accepting another culture.

Man is universal through school. The interaction of culture with the family and social environment determines the developmental profile of the individual. Migration and migration agents have always existed. They do not respect borders and territories. Their proposed revision leads to new interpretations, assigning participants, multiple membership meanings. The schemas of first-generation immigrants reinterpret their own culture by combining it with the cultural characteristics of society, while their descendants are receptors of new cultural paradigms, reinterpreting it after a set of cultural information (customs) inherited from their parents. .

Accommodating other people's cultures is not simple, it involves several steps:

knowledge;

acceptance;

non-verbal communication;

environment;

reporting on time.

A model based on cultural transmission is proposed: vertical transmission from self, oblique transmission from parents, horizontal transmission from birth. Cross-cultural communication requires patience and there will be initial time. Cultural comparison with contact with a foreign culture, intercultural education, is the main feature of any educational program.

The novelty value of translations and interpretations based on intersemiotic exercises requires the formation of intercultural competence.

People in contact with other cultures realize a symbiosis between the old cultural experience and the innovation created by the other culture.

Everything is through the eyes and tools of existing cultural schemas it seems Stability and change are two components of intercultural communication. Internal changes due to external pressure results in Piaget's assimilation. Binding of the personal conditional world is controlled by several pacifications and assimilations. The transition from one culture to another involves several levels of educational achievement.

Actually the difference is at the institutional level, at the group level, at the relational level, at the psychological level. The greatest achievement of multiculturalism is the anti-global homogenization reaction. The 70s brought openness to cultural pluralism years. The school faced an undeniable fact: mass migration, schooling and socio-professional integration of newcomers (children and parents), children from different nationalities, different cultures, without losing sight of the local population. It arose from the assimilation of

differences or the denial of the right to cultivate one's customs, traditions, and language. Intercultural education is based on school-family cooperation and continuous training for different cultures, and as a result of the evaluation of the codes of staff who have the same home as the children, individual helps to explore the differentiated roots in psychology. Do not overlook the fact that the school aims to provide an equal exchange between cultures and to harmonize cultural and social relations. Intercultural education should take into account substantive knowledge and interpersonal relationships. Based on the dialogue between cultures, despite the differences, the role of education is to develop a relationship of solidarity, openness, acceptance, enrichment and learning of diversity, new acceptance, recognition and cooperation, dialogue.

Migration, development and diversification of information and communication networks, globalization create a complex modern society and force teachers to adapt to the new reality. If the school wants to form a universal

consciousness, the teacher must revise his method and take into account cultural differences, from these differences. works with parents to avoid conflicts arising from cultural differences. People can act and interact with individuals and cultures. Because of their curiosity and curiosity, their behavior is related to new media and communication. lead within the dominant norms and values that characterize companies, want to know and understand more about what they see or visit.

The native culture acquired through education, socialization, traditions, values and norms of the society of origin causes problems of adaptation, integration, communication to the real culture shock in contact with different value systems. Interactions in the economic, military, and cultural spheres went hand in hand, creating spheres of cultural interference depending on your historical and geopolitical context. Remembering that the twentieth century witnessed two world wars, there were ample opportunities for confrontation and

cross-cultural exchange, not to mention the current conflicts, their civilizational and religious dimensions.

1. The struggle for resources, globalization, migration and capital flows have created a favorable interaction between cultures. Global economy, global security, global communication facilitated by new technologies meet new needs.

2. Approaches and intercultural conflicts have become a daily reality based on the acquisition of skills, competences and competencies.

Individuals must create relatively new multiple identities in relation to social contexts, political and cultural issues. A typical case of cross-cultural communication is depicted by immigrants, who go through several experiences as they move through moments that oscillate between drama and true culture shock to adaptation and integration into a new society. Just knowing the differences between each other (politeness, accuracy, how to be and speak, feelings and how they live and look, customs, clothes, religion, attitude to family, education, government) leads to intercultural communication based on cultural values.

3. In different situations, whether we travel as a tourist, or when we want to settle as an immigrant, or daily experience must be related to the outside, behind the scenes, background facts with values. Acquiring intercultural competence involves managing the overlaps and differences between these dual realities. The role of education is to prepare young people to understand and accept differences, to be open and tolerant, to cooperate and to communicate effectively with partners from other cultural fields. Educational Pioneers must strive to protect cultural differences and create an environment conducive to their coexistence for the benefit of human progress. Managing lessons and reconciling conflicting cultural differences and different identities is one of the challenges of the modern world.

4. The school represents a space where human development is achieved through education in which the observance of common values, personal

and social communication are accepted unanimously. Communicating about the components of intercultural communication is a mandatory requirement of modern society. People need to be prepared for the reality of multiculturalism of choices and institutions; and in turn, they should welcome those who value different codes. The world is for cultural clashes and interventions. is the ground. Intercultural education puts the teacher in a position to negotiate values, behaviors, and concerns between students and teachers as a result of opening access to deviating from the norm and affirming the freedom of multiple identities. Clash of cultures and cultural communication are complex at the social and educational levels determines the situations. 5. Mitigating divisions through education for a new world order

possible Interculturalism is a new challenge for education in the context of the economic, political and cultural characteristics of the European continent. Also, any type of intolerance can disappear if it is promoted within the framework of intercultural behavior. A multicultural society is based on integration, provides members with cultural security and gives everyone an equal opportunity to participate in economic and intercultural education through schooling, we deny the

formation of cultural attitudes and behaviors that are formed in response to cultural pluralism. we observe with an inexhaustible integrative quality.

References:

1. Nedelcu, A. 2008. Fundamentals of intercultural education, Iași: Polyrom, pp. 28-32
2. Georgiou, G. 2010. Comunicare interculturală. Probleme, abordări, teorii, Bucharest: Comunicare.ro, p. 121
3. Ilie, G. 2014. Oferta educațională și gârăța prămării. Интре дезезиблибру ши corelare, Craiova: Editura Sitech, p. 29
4. Williamson, O. The New Institutional Economics: Taking Stock, Looking Ahead/O. Williamson // Journal of Economic Literature. - 2000.- № 3. -Pp. 595-613.
5. Torres, R. Innovación y Tecnología: necesidad de cambios en los procesos de enseñanza, aprendizaje, inclusión de competencias y compromisos desde la formación docente/R. Torres // Vivat Academia. - 2012. - No. 817-Pp. 1520-1544.
6. Reiman, Alan J. What does innovation mean for moral educators? / Alan J. Reiman, H. Dotger Benjamin // Journal of Moral Education, 2008. -Vol. 37. -№ 2. Pp.151-164.